

and the outermost cell walls. In general, iron coatings appear as porous or dense materials filling the lumens (Photo 1). In a rare case, FeOOH precipitated into lumens with all the cell walls intact and formed an iron cast the shape of the original epidermal cell (Photo 2). The hollow interior on the left cast with a broken end indicates that precipitation begins on the cell walls. No visible coating showed on younger secondary roots and sections of roots near the tips. ■

1. Representative view of iron coating on rice root. L: lumen, I: iron coating.

2. Special case of iron coating formation. IC: iron casts of epidermal cells, E: broken end of a cast.

Performance of new rice entries at different planting dates and nitrogen rates

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The timely planting of rice is important in testing the yield level of any rice variety because it enables the plant to utilize more efficiently the environment in which it is grown. In general early planting (first week of June) of medium-duration varieties results in higher yield. In case of short-duration varieties, planting time does not greatly affect the grain yield of rice. A field experiment at the Crop Research Centre of G. B. Pant University of Agriculture & Technology, Pantnagar, during 1977 kharif tested the performance of newly developed rice varieties.

Effect of planting dates on grain yield of rice varieties grown under different levels of nitrogen. Pantnagar, India, 1977 kharif.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ ha)					
	1 June		16 June		1 July	
	60 kg N/ ha	120 kg N/ ha	60 kg N/ ha	120 kg N/ ha	60 kg N/ ha	120 kg N/ ha
Jaya	6.1	6.7	6.2	6.9	5.5	6.5
UPR103 D-6-1	5.5	6.5	5.3	5.6	4.4	4.8
UPR171-12	5.3	6.5	5.2	6.4	5.4	5.8
UPR73-23	6.0	6.7	6.0	6.3	5.5	5.9
IET2815	5.9	6.8	6.1	6.7	5.1	6.4
Ratna	5.9	6.7	6.1	6.2	6.5	5.5
Saket 4	6.1	6.7	6.4	6.3	5.3	6.0
UPR4-D-1-1	6.3	6.3	5.4	5.6	5.2	5.6
UPR82-1-7	5.6	6.3	6.1	6.2	5.7	5.9
IR36	6.2	7.0	5.6	6.4	5.3	6.0
			S.Em.±	C.D. at 5%	C.V. (%)	
Date × nitrogen × variety			0.23	0.64	7	
Nitrogen × variety			0.13	0.37		

Jaya gave maximum yield when planted on 16 June; UPR103-D-61, UPR1 71-12, UPR73-23, UPR4-D-1-1, and IR36 gave higher yields when planted on 1 June, irrespective of nitro-

gen dose. Ratna, Saket 4, IET2815, UPR82-1-7 yielded more when planted 16 June with 60 kg N/ ha than when planted 1 July with 120 kg N/ha (see table). ■

Neem cake-blended urea for increased nitrogen use efficiency in transplanted rice

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When nitrogen fertilizers are added to soil, their efficiency is reduced considerably — sometimes to the extent of 50%

or less — because of leaching, denitrification, volatilization, and surface runoff. There is a need for some simple and cheap device to reduce these losses. One device found effective under the different soil conditions prevailing in Karnataka is blending ordinary urea with nonedible neem cake available locally. Neem (*Azadirachta indica*) trees grow abundantly in India.

The technique consists of mixing well-powdered, country-pressed neem cake

with ordinary urea (30% by wt). Adherence of neem cake powder to urea granules is very important in the blending process. To ensure that, the powder and granules are mixed well 1 or 2 days ahead of application. The mixture is incorporated uniformly in equal doses at the time of planting and tilling.

Better adherence of neem cake to urea granules is obtained by using a coal tar (used for road surfacing) and kerosene oil mixture in 1:2 proportions while